

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN
INDONESIA”**

Dilakukan secara daring, 23-24 Oktober 2021

PROSIDING ADIWIDYA 9

SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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Water Conservation Using Rainwater Harvesting System in Urban Mosque for Sustainable Infrastructure

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Abstract. Today the urban cities are facing increased water stress especially for available water resources. Water resources is not only used for domestic purposes, but also for non-domestic purposes or public facilities. One example of a public facility that uses water to meet daily needs is a mosque. In urban infrastructure has mosque as moeslem worship places and the building need to be environmentally sustainable. Rainwater harvesting system is one method for water conservation and relate for sustainable infrastructure. Rainwater harvesting has a pre-eminent role to play and utilization of rainwater and also to reduce run off. By looking at this condition, rainwater should be utilized optimally. This aim study for planning of rainwater harvestingsystem at mosque with the main purpose of this planning being as an alternative to clean water and minimizing the use of ground water for water conservation. The data needed in planning the rainwater harvesting system are data on water demand, rainfall, and as built drawings. After the calculation, the components of the rainwater harvesting system design are obtained, namely storage tanks (3,100 L), gutters (6 inches), first flush diverter (4 inches with a length of 7 meters), and piping systems(4 inches). The construction of this rainwater harvesting system is expected as an alternative to minimize the use of ground water and clean water supplies in the future, especially the need for clean water for worship places.

1. Introduction

The increase in urban population has an impact on the increasing water demand and the number of public facilities. Public facilities that must exist in one city such as health facilities, educational facilities, places of worship, and others. The use of clean water is not only used for domestic purposes but also for non-domestic needs or public facilities. One example of public facilities that use water to meet daily needs is a mosque. Based on data obtained from BPS (2020) [5], Indonesia is the country with the most Muslim population in the world. As a country with a majority of Muslims, then one of the water needs in the future is the need for water to worship.

Airan Raya Mosque is one of the places of worship located in the south Lampung regency area. The mosque was established in 2016 and has a strategic location. Over time, the infrastructure and activities around The Airan Raya Mosque are increasing, such as the Airan Raya Mosque is close to the Sumatra Institute of Technology College, Sukarame Police, Lampung Police, and located at the Kotabaru Toll Gate. So, The Airan Raya Mosque can be used as a place to perform prayers both fardhu prayers and Friday prayers by the surrounding community and travelers. This certainly has an impact on the problem of the quantity and continuity of clean water that occurs in the Airan Raya Mosque.

The water source used by the Airan Raya Mosque to fulfill daily activities comes from groundwater. Excessive use of groundwater sources by using drill wells can cause the availability of groundwater to be drastically reduced. Exploitation of groundwater can also cause clean water difficulties because groundwater is increasingly difficult to obtain. Rainwater harvesting system is included in one of the simple technologies, the concept of rainwater harvesting can be used as an alternative source of clean water so as to reduce the use of groundwater.

Based on the description above, then to overcome the problem of clean water needs in the future, technology needs to be developed about alternative water sources. One technology that can be applied is rainwater harvesting technology. Rainwater harvesting technology is a simple technology and can be used as an effort to reduce the use of groundwater in the Airan Raya Mosque. Therefore, the author plans the application of rainwater harvesting technology at the Airan Raya Mosque with the final result in the form of a concept and design of rainwater harvesting system.

2. Methods

In this study, the case study used is a place of worship, namely Airan Raya Mosque located on Jalan Airan Raya, Way Huwi Village, Jati Agung District, South Lampung Regency, Lampung. The research phase starts from field studies, data collection, data processing and discussion, and conclusions. This research also covers the technical aspects of the design of rainwater harvesting at the Airan Raya Mosque. The data needed in this study include water needs data, as built drawing Masjid Airan Raya, and rain data. The rain data used in this study is daily rainfall data from two rain stations, namely sukarama rain station and way galih rain station.

2.1. Water Demand

Calculation of clean water needs is done to find out the amount of water needed by the Airan Raya Mosque every day. Calculation of clean water needs can be done using Equation 1.

$$B = D \times P \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Where B is water demand (liters), D is water demand per person per day (Liters/person), and P is number of pilgrims (person)

2.2. Hydrological Analysis

In this study hydrological analysis is needed to determine the maximum daily rainfall and intensity of rain in a certain period of time. The stages in hydrological analysis are regional rainfall, rainfall frequency analysis, maximum daily rainfall analysis, match testing analysis and rain intensity analysis. The results of this stage will be used to calculate the dimensions of the components of the rainwater harvesting system at the Airan Raya Mosque. Calculation of rain intensity can be done using equation 2.

$$I = \frac{R_{24}}{24} \left(\frac{24}{t} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad \dots\dots (2)$$

Where I is intensity of rain (mm/hour) , R is maximum daily rainfall (mm), t is duration of rainfall (hours).

2.3. Analysis of The Volume of Rainwater That Can Be Accommodated

Calculation of the volume of rainwater that can be accommodated is done to find out how much rainwater can be accommodated. The amount of rainwater that can be accommodated is influenced by several factors including rainfall that occurs in South Lampung, the area of the rain catchment, and the coefficient of runoff.

$$S = R \times A \times C \quad \dots\dots(3)$$

Where S is supply demand (Liters), R is rainfall (mm), A is roof area (m²), C is coefficient runoff.

2.4. Calculation of Dimensions of Rainwater Harvesting System Components

In general, the components of a rainwater harvesting system consist of an capture area, a distribution system, and a storage tank. The determination of the concept of units needed in the research of rainwater harvesting systems in the Airan Raya Mosque is adjusted to the existing conditions of the mosque building. In this study, the components of the system that need to be calculated dimensions are a) gutters and piping; b) first flush diverter; c) storage tank.

2.4.1. Gutter and Piping

The dimensions of the gutter that will be used in the planning of the rainwater harvesting system at the Airan Raya Mosque are guided by SNI 8153-2015 about the Plumbing System in buildings. If the magnitude of the value of the intensity of the planned rainfall is not contained in the SNI table, then to determine the area of the planned roof can be calculated using Equation 4.

$$\text{Area of catchment area for planned intensity} = \frac{\text{Catchment area intensity } 25.4 \text{ mm / hour}}{\text{Desired intensity } (\frac{\text{mm}}{\text{hour}}) / 25.4 \text{ mm/hour}} \dots\dots(4)$$

2.4.2. First Flush Diverter

The first flush diverter used was cylindrical of a pipe consisting of an upright pipe and a ball. In determining the dimensions of the upright pipe used as the first flush diverter refers to SNI 8153-2005. The equation used is equation 4 if the amount of planned rainfall intensity is not contained in the SNI table.

2.4.3. Storage Tank

In this planning to determine the volume capacity of storage tanks used a method of balance between water supply and water demand (water balance). The main rule in determining the size of the volume of storage tanks is that the volume of rainwater that can be accommodated must be equal to or exceed the demand for water needs. The equation in determining the volume of the storage tank is:

$$V = S - B \dots\dots (5)$$

Where V is storage tank volume (m³), S is supply water (m³), B is water demand (m³)

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Water Demand

The basic planning used in accounting for the volume of water demand is to use the method of number of users. According to RSNI T-01-2003) each pilgrim spends about 15 liters of water per day. Based on the results of field surveys for one week, the calculation of water needs in the Airan Raya Mosque in one day can be done by multiplying the number of worshipers in one day by the standard of water use per day through equation 1. Here are the water needs at the Airan Raya Mosque on Monday :

$$B = D \times P$$

$$B = 15 \text{ liters/person/day} \times 183 \text{ person}$$

$$B = 2,745 \text{ liters/day}$$

$$B = 2.745 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$$

Table 3.1 Recapitulation of daily water use

Days	Number Of Pilgrims (person)	Standard Daily Water Usage (Liters)	Water Use (Liters)
Monday	183	15	2745
Tuesday	193	15	2895
Wednesday	178	15	2670
Thursday	178	15	2670
Friday	587	15	8805
Saturday	200	15	3000
Sunday	233	15	3495
Sum			26280
Average			3754

From Table 3.1 it can be known that the total water use in one week is 26,280 liters or 26.28 m³ and the average daily water use is 3,754 liters or 3.754 m³.

3.2. Hydrological Analysis

The rain data used is rain data with observation periods over the last 10 years, starting from 2011 to 2020. Based on the distance of the rainfall observation post from the research site and the availability of data, two rain posts were selected obtained from Balai Besar Wilayah Sungai (BBWS) Mesuji-Way Sekampung. Based on the analysis of rainfall frequency, analysis of maximum daily rainfall, and match test, then the selected distribution method is gumbel distribution method. Based on these data, the intensity of rain for PUH 5 years with a duration of 2 hours is 26.496 mm / hour.

Table 3.2 Maximum rainfall plan

Year	Maximum Rainfall Plan (mm)	Year	Maximum Rainfall Plan (mm)
2011	38	2016	61.7
2012	42	2017	81.5
2013	143.5	2018	56.5
2014	36.5	2019	155
2015	56.6	2020	87.5

3.3. Analysis of The Volume of RainWater That Can Be Accommodated

In this study, the volume of rainwater that can be accommodated to find out how much rainwater availability to meet the needs of clean water in the Airan Raya Mosque. The amount of the value of water availability or the volume of rainwater that can be accommodated is influenced by the amount of rainfall that occurs in Lampung, the area of the building roof as a rain catchment area, and the coefficient of runoff. The rain data used is the maximum rain data that occurred in 2019 to be exact in December. Here is an example of the calculation for December 1, 2019 :

$$S = R \times A \times C$$

$$S = 6 \text{ mm} \times 1050 \text{ m}^2 \times 0.85 \times \frac{1 \text{ m}}{1000 \text{ mm}}$$

$$S = 5.36 \text{ m}^3$$

The same calculation was carried out for December 2, 2019 to December 31, 2019. Based on the results of calculations, it is known that the availability of rainwater that can be accommodated in the Airan Raya Mosque is 243.92 m³.

3.4. Design of Rainwater Harvesting System at Airan Raya Mosque

3.4.1 Gutter and Piping

In determining the design of gutters and piping the value of rain intensity used is the maximum rain intensity with a duration of rain for 2 hours and the intensity of rain with a PUH of 5 years. The result of calculating the area of catchment for the intensity of the planned rain is 26.496 mm / hour using Equation 5. So for the roof area of the Airan Raya Mosque of 1,050 m² used gutters with a size of 5 inches. However, when viewed from the availability of gutter size in the market, then in the planning of the rainwater harvesting system in the Airan Raya Mosque used gutters with a size of 6 inches.

3.4.2 First Flush Diverter

The first flush diverter used in the study took the form of an upright pipe consisting of an inlet and outlet. The first flush diverter components used in this planning are fabrications available in the market. Determination of the pipe diameter of the first flush diverter unit is done with reference to SNI 8153-2015. Thus, the size of the diameter of the upright pipe for the first flush diverter in this study is an upright pipe with a size of 4 inches and a length of 7 m.

3.4.3 Storage Tank

Storage tanks are the main component in the planning of rainwater harvesting systems. This is because storage tank components require the most cost compared to other components. Therefore, it is very important to plan the appropriate storage tank capacity in order to save costs. Determination of the dimensions or volume of rainwater

storage tanks in this planning is done using the method of balance between water supply and water demand (water balance) in The Airan Raya Mosque. Here is an example of a calculation for December 1, 2019 :

$$V = S - B$$

$$V = 5.36 \text{ m}^3 - 3.754 \text{ m}^3$$

$$V = 1,61 \text{ m}^3$$

Furthermore, it was done in the same way for December 2, 2019 to December 31, 2019. So, in the planning of the rainwater harvesting system at the Airan Raya Mosque was obtained the required storage tank volume size of $3.15 \text{ m}^3 / \text{day}$. In the planning of the rainwater harvesting system at the Masjid Airan Raya the storage tank used is a storage tank with a size of 3,100 liters.

Picture 3.1 Front view of the rainwater harvesting system at the Airan Raya mosque

3.5. Maintenance of Rainwater Harvesting System

3.6. The process of maintaining and monitoring the rainwater harvesting system needs to be done periodically so that the rainwater harvesting system can be implemented sustainably and ensure that no damage can interfere with the running of the system. The treatment and monitoring process that needs to be done can be seen in the Table. 3.3

Table 3.3 Maintenance Of Rainwater Harvesting System

No	Component	Type Of Maintenance	Period
1	Roof	Ensure the roof is in good condition and does not leak or rust.	6 month
2	Gutter	Ensure the condition of the gutter is good and not damaged. In addition, make sure the gutter condition is no blockage and the entire gutter connection is not loose.	6 month
3	First Flush Diverter	Ensure the unit is not damaged and does not leak	6 month

No	Component	Type Of Maintenance	Period
4	Storage Tank	Ensure the tank doesn't leak and crack	6 month
		Drain the tank periodically	1 x 2 month and at the beginning of the rainy season or the transition of the seasons
5	Filtration	Wash or replace the filter media	1 x 1 month or according to needs

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of calculations and planning, in this study, the volume of rainwater that can be harvested by the roof of the Airan Raya Mosque based on the calculation results is 243.92 m³ per month. As for the water demand at the Airan Raya Mosque is 3,754 liters/day, the specifications of the planned rainwater harvesting system are a storage tank with a size of 3,100 liters, a rectangular gutter with a size of 6 inches, and a first flush diverter with a size of 4 inches and 7m long.

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